

EFFECT OF METALAXYL AND NEEM SEED OIL ON THE INCIDENCE OF DOWNY MILDEW OF PEARL MILLET

¹Aliyu, B., ²Hati, S. S., ³Donli, P.O. and ⁴Anaso, A. B.

¹Department of Biological Sciences, ²Department of Chemistry, Gombe State University, Gombe
³Department of Biological Sciences, ⁴Department of Crop Science, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri

ABSTRACT

Millet is one of the most important staple food crops in Africa and India. The grain yield losses as a result of downy mildew disease varied from 10 to 50% annually. This study was aimed at determining the effect of seed treatment with metalaxyl either alone or in combination with neem seed oil foliar sprays on the incidence of pearl millet downy mildew. Field trials were carried out in 2006 and 2007 growing seasons. Split - plot design was employed with four categories of chemical treatments and three varieties of pearl millet (SOSAT-C88, EX-Borno and GB8735). The treatments were in triplicates. The results of the study showed that incidence of downy mildew on vegetative shoots of pearl millet differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) among the varieties studied. Generally, SOSAT-C88 showed significant resistance to downy mildew than the other varieties. As anticipated, the combination of metalaxyl and neem oil spray significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the incidence of downy mildew on pearl millet and improved yield compared to the neem oil spray alone and the control during the 2006 season. From this study, metalaxyl was found to be still an effective fungicide against downy mildew in pearl millet. However, supplementing metalaxyl with neem oil spray generally increased grain yield.

KEYWORDS: downy mildew, pearl millet, metalaxyl, neem oil

INTRODUCTION

Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L) R. Br.) is one of the most important staple food crops in Africa and India (Williams, 1984), and is grown as a subsistent crop in the Sudano-Sahalian Savanna of northern Nigeria. The grain is nutritious and contains 5-7% oil. It has higher protein level and more mineral constituent than maize and rice (NRC, 1996). The arable land put to pearl millet in West Africa has been estimated to be 23.99 million hectares; and in Nigeria it is about 5 million hectares, which places Africa as the third largest producer of the world's pearl millet (FAO, 1985). It yields relatively well in regions too hot and too dry to support good yield of maize and sorghum (NRC, 1996). Millet in Nigeria is predominantly produced in Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Kano, Katsina, Sokoto and Yobe States.

Apart from the harsh environmental conditions which limit the crop's production potentials, pearl millet is attacked by various diseases and pests in the field. The most important of the fungal diseases of pearl millet is downy mildew, caused by the fungus (*Sclerospora graminicola* (Sacc.) Schroet), which has been estimated to cause losses of 10 – 15% in Nigeria. Other diseases of pearl millet in Nigeria are smut (*Moesziomyces pennicullariae* (Bref)) Vankysyn. (*Tolysporium pennisscullariae* (Bref)) and ergot (*Claviceps fusiformis* (Loveless) (Thakur and King, 1988) while important invertebrate pests include stem borer (*Coniesta ignefusalis*), head miner (*Raghuva* sp), the head beetle (*Pacnoda* sp) and grasshoppers while *Quelea quelea* is the major vertebrate pest and parasitic flowering plant, *Striga* (Rai and Kumar, 1994).

Yield losses of up to 50% due to downy mildew have been reported from West Africa (Singh *et al.*, 1987). An annual loss due to downy mildew in Nigeria was put at 10% (King and Webster, 1970). Waller and Ball (1982) reported consistent disease incidence of 10-15%.

Wheeler (1979) reported that downy mildew is controlled chiefly by cultural methods, by spraying fungicides and by planting less susceptible varieties. It is, however, by the application of fungicides that the most practical control of this disease had been achieved. Anaso *et al.* (1989) reported that maize downy mildew is successfully controlled by seed treatment with metalaxyl and host resistance. Nene and Singh (1976) noted that two methods of chemical control of pearl millet downy mildew had been attempted, one was treatment of seed with fungicide to control seed borne inocula and the second method was the use of foliar sprays to control secondary spread.

Metalaxyl is a known fungicide for seed treatment to control downy mildew, its action is systemic and contains benzenoid (phenylamide), used in mixtures as a foliar spray for tropical and subtropical crops, as a soil treatment for control of soil-borne pathogens, and as a seed treatment to control downy mildews (Kimmel, *et al.*, 1986). Similarly, neem oil, a vegetable oil pressed from the fruits and seeds of [neem](#) (*Azadirachta indica*), have scientifically been validated for many of its traditional uses to treat bacterial, fungal, and viral infections, including its use as pesticides (Schmutterer, 2002). The neem tree is found in abundance in northern Nigeria and the seed's oil is thought to be very likely to effectively control downy mildew of pearl millet. The neem seed oil is known to contain nearly 100 protolimonoids, limonoids or tetranortriterpenoids, pentanortriterpenoids, hexanortriterpenoids and some nonterpenoid constituents. Different batches contain from 1700 ppm azadirachtin to 2500 ppm azadirachtin as the active ingredients. The oil contains small amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and other nutrients. It also contains the following fatty acids - Palmitic acid 19.4%, Stearic acid 21.2%, Oleic acid 42.1%, Linoleic acid 14.9% and Arachidic acid 1.4% (Conrick and Schmutterer, 2004).

In northern Nigeria, pearl millet is regarded as second only to sorghum in importance. The grain is used in a variety of traditional foods such as "fura", "biski", "masa", "yartsala", "tuwo", "kunu", "burukutu" and "pito". Its production supercedes that of sorghum because of its outstanding ability to withstand drought, its early maturing advantages over other crops and it is the first grain crop grown by farmers in Northern Nigeria in anticipation of early grain for consumption when other reserved grain become exhausted (Nwasike *et al.*, 1983). In view of the decreasing level of production emanating from the constraints already highlighted, it was therefore considered essential to carry out a study that would assess the potentials of seed treatment with metalaxyl and neem seed oil either alone or in combination with neem seed oil as foliar sprays on the incidence of pearl millet downy mildew for the control of this disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Metalaxyl and Neem Seed Oil

Metalaxyl fungicide in Apron XL-LS brand manufactured by Syngenta Crop Protection Canada, Inc. was obtained and used in this study. This brand formulation is about 33.3% metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam) formulated as a liquid for use as a seed treatment in a container size: 1L, 5L and 55L

Neem oil was obtained from extraction according to method described by Kaura *et al* (1998). Petroleum ether (bp 60-80°C) was used as extraction solvent, which was recovered from filtrate by ordinary distillation at 70°C, further in rotary vacuum evaporator placed on a water bath for 20 hours at 60-70°C. After extraction the neem oil was diluted with different amount of liquid paraffin to obtain different concentrations of extracts.

Pearl Millet Seeds

Millet varieties, SOSAT-C88, Ex-Borno and GB 8735 used in this study were obtained from the germplasm bank of Lake Chad Research Institute, Maiduguri.

Experimental Site

The experiment was conducted during 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons in Maiduguri (Latitude 11⁰51' N; 13⁰ 15'E) at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Maiduguri.

The experimental site is a sandy loam and has been classified as typic ustipsamment. The mean annual rainfall range between 40 and 250mm with an annual average temperature ranges from 20-43°C. The area has been cropped with millet for the several years ensuring build up of disease inoculum. Natural epiphytotic in field was therefore relied upon as the source of inoculum in each season. The split - plot design was employed in this study.

Chemical Treatments

Chemical treatments of the pear millets were made in four categories:

1. Metalaxyl (0.4g) per 50g millet treatment prior to planting,
2. Metalaxyl (0.4g) per 50g millet treatment prior to planting + neem oil (0.3kg foliar spray)
3. Neem oil (0.3kg) foliar spray based on fungal LD₅₀ (Schmutterer, 2002) and
4. Control (neither metalaxyl nor neem seed oil)

The neem oil was dispensed using electrodyn sprayer on non rainy days. Triplicate plots treatments comprised three varieties namely, SOSAT-C88, Ex-Borno and GB 8735.

Cultural Practices and Management

The site was harrowed, disked and leveled before marking out the plots. The main plots were 12 X 4.0 m (48 m²) each and separated by 1m from each other were assigned to the chemical treatments (Fungicides). The sub-plot of 4 X 4 m (16 m²) and spaced at 0.5m comprised the three millet varieties.

The seeds were sown when the rains established at rate of ten seeds per hole and spaced at 75 X 30 cm between rows and within rows, respectively. At three weeks after sowing during the first weeding plants were thinned to two plants per stand.

Fertilizers were applied at the recommended rates of 60kg N/ha, 30kg P₂O₅/ha and 30kg K₂O/ha (Anaso, 1989). At planting, basal dose of NPK (15:15:15) at the rate of 48g N, 48g P₂O₅ and 48g K₂O were applied respectively to each plot. The remaining dose of 48gN was applied at six weeks after sowing by the side placement method. Weeds were controlled manually using hoes on the third and the sixth weeks after sowing. Harvest was done manually at maturity using cutlass. The plants were cut at their bases and placed in their respective plots for further drying after which the panicles were cut and threshed.

Parameters Measured

Millet stands in each plot were counted and recorded at 56 days after sowing. Grain yields for all treatments were obtained after harvesting, sun-drying, threshing and winnowing. They were then weighed on a Mettler balance (0-10kg) and yields per plot determined. The yields were later converted to kg/ha. The number and weight of panicles per plot were determined.

Downy Mildew Incidence on Vegetative Shoot

Infected main stems and basal tillers plants were counted at 56 days after sowing (DAS) and downy mildew incidence was computed as the number of diseased main stand or basal tillers expressed as percentage of the total number of main stands or basal tillers assessed according to James (1983) as follows:

Downy mildew incidence (%) = Number of diseased plants/plot ÷ Total number of plants/plot × 100

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), using Microsoft Excel (2003). Variations of results were considered significant at p<0.05.

RESULTS

The three varieties of pearl millet showed varied responses to downy mildew attack in the area of study. The incidence of downy mildew on vegetative shoots of pearl millet differed significantly (p<0.05) among the varieties studied (Table 1). The variety GB8735 showed high incidence compared to SOSAT-C88 and EX-Borno. The difference between SOSAT-C88 and EX-Born was not significant for the main stems and significantly different for basal tillers in both years (Table 1).

Among the fungicides applied the combination of metalaxyl and neem oil spray and metalaxyl alone significantly ($P<0.05$) reduced the incidence of downy mildew on pearl millet main stems compared to the neem oil spray alone and the control during the 2006 season (Table 1). A similar trend was observed on the basal tillers except that the difference between the application of neem oil spray and the control was not significant (Table 1).

The production of panicle and grain yield of pearl millet differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among the three varieties (Table 2). The varieties SOSAT-C88 and EX-Borno performed better in production of panicle and grain yield than GB8735 in the year 2006. in the following year the difference among the varieties was significant.

Table 1: Effects of variety and fungicide on the incidence of downy mildew on the vegetative shoots of pearl millet in Maiduguri during the 2006 and 2007 growing seasons

Treatment	% incidence of downy mildew on vegetative shoot			
	Main stems		Basal tillers	
	2006	2007	2006	2007
<u>Variety</u>				
SOSAT-C88	34.26±5.4	33.15±4.5	35.30±8.1	36.63±6.8
Ex-Borno	38.33±7.2	36.56±12.2	42.20±7.8	49.51±11.7
GB8735	45.57±7.8	55.30±10.3	52.88±9.4	59.80±12.2
<u>Fungicide</u>				
Neem oil spray (NOS)	46.60±6.7	43.88±5.4	51.82±8.3	56.26±10.4
Apron XL-LS	31.04±5.5	35.58±5.6	34.29±3.9	41.18±11.2
NOS + Apron XL-LS	28.04±7.2	36.67±5.9	32.15±2.4	36.56±7.4
Control	51.87±12.5	50.55±11.3	55.57±11.3	60.59±8.2

Table 2: Effects of variety and fungicide on number of panicles, panicle weight and grain yield of pearl millet in Maiduguri during the 2006 and 2007 growing seasons

Treatment	Number of panicles		Panicle weight (kg/ha)		Grain yield (kg/ha)	
	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007
<u>Variety</u>						
SOSAT-C88	91.00±21.2	97.33±10.6	2759±121.3	3117±211.8	1591±98.2	1852±154.9
Ex-Borno	80.33±16.3	84.42±11.5	2350±115.5	2628±117.5	1290±87.3	1231±119.3
GB8735	68.50±11.6	58.75±12.7	2033±211.4	1307±87.5	1021±66.8	938±32.4
<u>Fungicide</u>						
Neem oil spray (NOS)	68.67±12.3	74.90±12.4	1933±187.7	2325±213.2	1011±102.4	1179±106.7
Apron XL-LS	96.78±10.5	86.67±11.4	3075±219.1	2600±165.3	1708±121.5	1472±107.3
NOS + Apron XL-LS	99.56±9.8	93.11±16.8	3189±176.0	2700±142.4	1679±89.5	1737±98.9
Control	54.78±7.6	66.00±9.6	1322±113.4	1778±109.0	805±43.7	973±21.5

Table 3: Interaction of variety and fungicide on grain yield of pearl millet in Maiduguri during the 2007 growing season

Variety	Number of panicles			
	Neem oil spray (NOS)	Apron XL-LS	NOS + Apron XL-LS	Control
SOSAT-C88	1683±121.4	2006±154.7	2567±176.3	1150±88.2
Ex-Borno	1130±56.3	1295±113.4	1427±132.2	1070±66.2
GB8735	723±12.5	1113±102.1	1217±79.9	700±10.3

The production of panicle and grain yield was significantly influenced by the application of fungicide (Table 2). Plants treated with metalaxyl and metalaxyl + neem oil spray showed increased panicle size and grain yield than those received neem oil spray and the check.

The interaction effects of variety and fungicide on grain yield was significant (Table 3). The variety (SOSAT-C88) that produced the highest yield did so when treated with the combination of metalaxyl and neem oil spray. A general increase in yield of the other varieties was also observed. The most susceptible variety to downy mildew was GB8735.

DISCUSSION

The fact that three varieties of pearl millet showed varied responses to downy mildew attack in the area of study confirmed the influence of genotype difference, which is a factor in choosing germplasms for cultivation. The variety SOSAT-C88 showed comparatively higher resistance to downy mildew than EX-Borno and GB8735. Varietal differences in pearl millet have also been reported (Rathi and Panwar, 1997; Singh *et al.*, 1993). This study revealed that infection was higher at the basal tillers than on the main stems. This could be due to the proximity of tillers to soil where if contaminated may be a readily source of infection.

Metalaxyl is still an effective fungicide against downy mildew in pearl millet from this study and the report of Williams and Singh (1981). However, supplementing metalaxyl with neem oil spray would generally increase grain yield.

In pearl millet growing areas where there is infestation of downy mildew the variety SOSAT-C88 should be used with the application of metalaxyl + neem oil spray for a better return on cost of production. There is still the need to develop highly resistant varieties against downy mildew so that the extra cost of fungicide would be reduced if not eliminated.

REFERENCES

- Anaso, A.B. (1989): Variety selection and planting strategies of maize for control of sorghum downy mildew in *Nigeria Guinea Savanna Applied Agricultural Research* 3: 196-200.
- Anaso, A. B, Emechebe A. M., Tyagi, P. D. and Manzo, S. K. (1989): Assessment in yield due to sorghum downy mildew of maize in Nigeria Guinea Savanna *Tropical Pest Management* 301-303.
- Conrick, J. and H. Schmutterer (2004): The Neem Tree : The Ultimate Herb. The Neem Foundation web site – www.neemfoundation.org (access date: 23/11/2007)
- Food Agricultural Organization (FOA) (1985): Production Year Book. Rome, Italy 2-15.
- James, W. C. (1983): Crop loss assessment pages 130-143 in plant pathologist pocket book 2nd edition (A. Johnston and C. Booth Eds) Commonwealth Mycological Institute Kew.

Kaura, S. K., S. K. Gupta and J. B. Chowdhury (1998): Morphological and oil content variation in seeds of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. (Neem) from northern and western provenances of India. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*. 52 (4): 293-298

Kimmel, E. C., J. E. Casida and L. O. Ruzo (1986): Formamidine Insecticides and Chloroacetanilide Herbicides: Disubstituted Anilines and Nitrobenzenes as Mammalian Metabolites and Bacterial Mutagens, *J. Agri Food Chem* 34:157-161.

King, S. B. and Webster, O. J. (1970): Downy mildew of sorghum in Nigeria *India Phytopathology* 4: 212-319.

Microsoft Excel (2003): Microsoft® Office Excel 2003 (11.5612.5606) <http://support.microsoft.com/international.aspx>. USA.

National Research Council (NRC) (1996): Lost crops of Africa vol. 1 Grains National Academy Press Washington D.C. 36: 1-12.

Nene, Y. L. and Singh, S. D. (1976): Downy mildew and ergot of pearl millet, pest Africa and News Summaries Darker 22 (3): 366-385.

Nwasike, C. C., E. F. I. Baker and P. N. Egharevba (1983): The Potential for Improving Millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*) in farming systems of the Semi Arid Areas of Nigeria. *Agriculture and Environment* 7: 15-21.

Rai, K. N. and Kumar, K. A. (1994): Pearl millet improvement at ICRISAT an Update International sorghum and millets Newsletter 35: 1-29.

Rathi, A. S. and Panwar, M. S. (1997): Downy Mildew reactions of pearl millet varieties and parents. *International Sorghum and Millets News Letter* No. 38, 128-130.

Schmutterer, H. (2002): *The Neem Tree: Source of Unique Natural Products for Integrated Pest Management, Medicine, Industry And Other Purposes (Hardcover)*, 2nd Edition, Weinheim, Germany: VCH Verlagsgesellschaft .ISBN 3-527-30054-6 P. 23-42

Singh, S. D., Balls, S. L. and Thakur, D. P. (1987): Problems and strategies in the control of downy mildew (a review article). *Proceedings of the International Pearl millet Workshop* International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics, Patancheru AP (India) 161-172.

Singh, S. D., King, S. B. and Werder, J. (1993): Downy mildew disease of pearl millet. *International Bulletin International crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics* (India) 37: 25-35.

Thakur, R.P. and King, S. B. (1988). Downy mildew disease of pearl millet, Information Bulletin No.2 International Crops Research Institute of Semi-Arid Tropics India 5-17.

Waller, J. M. and Ball, S. L. (1983): Interaction Between pearl millet varieties and *Sclerospora graminicola*. Plenum Press London. 5-20.

Wheeler, B. E. J. (1979): An introduction to Plant Disease Imperial College London, 12 : 350-373.

Williams, R. J. (1984): Downy mildew of tropical cereals. *Advance in Plant Pathology* 2: 1-03.

Williams, R. J. and Singh S. D. (1981): Control of pearl millet downy mildew by seed treatment with metalaxyl. *Annals of Applied Biology* 97: 263-268.

Aliyu, B *et al*: Continental J. Agronomy 2: 1 - 7, 2008

Received for Publication: 07/05/2008

Accepted for Publication: 24/05/2008

Corresponding Author:

Aliyu, B.

Department of Biological Sciences, Gombe State University, P.M.B. 127, Gombe, Nigeria

aliyubabale@yahoo.com